

RATIONING OF NURSING CARE AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO NURSE PRACTICE ENVIRONMENT IN A LEVEL 2 PRIVATE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Nursing activities are often forced to be prioritized to address medical needs and promote patient safety thereby omitting other significant activities like documentation and emotional support. Moreover, withholding, limiting or omitting holistic care significantly contributes to high mortality rate, undesirable patient outcomes, increased risks for nosocomial infections and falls, risks for pressure ulcer, and dampened quality of medical care which should be the top priority in healthcare (Tomaszewska, Majchrowic, & Ratusznik, 2021). A healthy work environment refers to one in which nurses can meet work goals and objectives while personally enjoying performing their job in their workplace. However, shortage of nursing staff, job dissatisfaction, low productivity, poor quality of nurse's work lives and precarious patient care can all be associated to deficiency for a productive and a healthy workplace (Flaubert et al, 2021). This study used analytical, cross-sectional study design as it aims to determine the rationing of nursing care and its relationship to nurse practice environment. In this study, the researchers aim to determine the level of rationing of implicit nursing care, the relationship of nursing care rationing and nurses' practice environment and if there is a relationship between nursing care rationing and nurse-related variables. This can be thought of as a "snapshot" of the frequency and characteristics of a condition in a population at a particular point in time. This study provides knowledge about the levels of rationing of care and its relationship to nurse practice in a level 2 private hospital. **The result of the study shows that there is no significant relationship between the rationing of nursing care and the nurse practice environment.** The majority of the respondents involved in the study had low

levels of correlating demographic profile and work environment practice which showed relatively no significance on their level of adherence to nursing care.

Keywords: *Nursing Care, Rationing, Nurse Practice*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Rationing is defined as the “wise allocation of scarce resources, which in health care necessarily entails withholding potentially beneficial treatments from some clienteles” (Scheunemann & White, 2011). In nursing, rationing pertains to discontinuation or abandonment of certain aspects of patient care that should have been done by nurses while on shift due to lack of time and resources (Zúñiga, et al., 2015). This inevitable phenomenon is present worldwide for it is challenging to deliver adequate health care services to certain clienteles due to limited resources and unlimited demands. Thus, rationing and priority setting have to be applied.

Nursing activities are often forced to be prioritized to address medical needs and promote patient safety thereby omitting other significant activities like documentation and emotional support. Moreover, withholding, limiting or omitting holistic care significantly contributes to high mortality rate, undesirable patient outcomes, increased risks for nosocomial infections and falls, risks for pressure ulcer, and dampened quality of medical care which should be the top priority in healthcare (Tomaszewska, Majchrowic, & Ratusznik, 2021).

Multitude of factors relating to the patient and nurse as well as the COVID- 19 pandemic affect the level of nursing care rationing which encompass heavy demands in the work environment, reduction of employment, burn-out and fatigue experienced by HCW, new treatment modalities, nurses attitude (which include their knowledge, beliefs and opinions), organizational resources, the patient himself/herself or associated risks while taking care of patients especially during this pandemic and the work environment (Jankowska-Polańska et al., 2021).

A healthy work environment refers to one in which nurses can meet work goals and objectives while personally enjoying performing their job in their workplace. However, shortage of nursing staff, job dissatisfaction, low productivity, poor quality of nurse’s work lives and precarious patient care can all be associated to deficiency for a productive and a healthy workplace (Flaubert, 2021).

Unfortunately, there is insufficient knowledge on the occurrence of implicit nursing care rationing in the country as well as factors that in one way or another contributes to its occurrence. Despite the fact that nurses work environment is a time-honored and well-researched topic in nursing, there is still lacking published studies that examines its significant relationship to the rationing of nursing care especially in private hospitals and other localities in the Philippines. Thus, this study aims to address this research gap.

The goal of this study is to determine the relationship between rationing of care and nurses work environment as an initial step towards developing relevant interventions and programs in the future. Also, it envisions to enlighten our government and other concerned parties in regards to these issues currently challenging our nurses in their respective work environment and on how they should deal with the possible outcomes of their actions that would affect the quality of patient care.

Research Objectives

Specifically, this study aims to determine the rationing of nursing care and its relationship to the nurse practice environment in Remedios Trinidad Romualdez Hospital on the following aspects: (a) Determining the level of rationing of nursing care; (b) Determining the relationship of nursing care rationing and nurses' practice environment; and (c) Determining the relationship between nursing care rationing and nurse-related variables.

METHODOLOGY

This study used analytical, cross-sectional study design as it aims to determine the rationing of nursing care and its relationship to nurse practice environment. In this study, the researchers aim to determine the level of rationing of implicit nursing care, the relationship of nursing care rationing and nurses' practice environment and if there is a relationship between nursing care rationing and nurse-related variables. This can be thought of as a “snapshot” of the frequency and characteristics of a condition in a population at a particular point in time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Patient quality care development, which has become a key focus for all healthcare providers, is one of the biggest healthcare hurdles to achieving a high degree of patient satisfaction. The variations in internal and external elements mostly determine the standard of medical care such as resource accessibility, patient cooperation, and collaboration between health professionals.

Rationing in nursing relates to termination or abandonment of some patient care tasks that nurses should have completed during their shifts because of a lack of time and resources. Withholding, limiting or omitting holistic care significantly contributes to high mortality rate, undesirable patient outcomes, increased risks for nosocomial infections and falls, risks for pressure ulcer, and dampened Quality of medical care which should be the top priority in healthcare (Tomaszewska, Majchrowic, & Ratusznik, 2021).

In order for nurses to fulfill their professional goals and objectives while also enjoying their work environment, a healthy work environment is needed. However, shortage of nursing staff, job dissatisfaction, low productivity, poor quality of nurse's work lives and precarious patient care can all be associated to deficiency for a productive and

a healthy workplace (Babapour, 2022).

In this study, a sample of 40 respondents was randomly selected Filipino nurses working in selected wards of a Level II Private Hospital' in Tacloban City. The relationship between rationing of nursing care and nurse practice environment in a level 2 private hospital, will be assessed by utilizing questionnaires in gathering the data. The result of the data gathered provided us with wide information about the relationship between rationing of nursing care and nurse practice environment in a level 2 private hospital.

Conclusions

This study provides knowledge about the levels of rationing of care and its relationship to nurse practice in a level 2 private hospital. **The result of the study shows that there is no significant relationship between the rationing of nursing care and the nurse practice environment.** The majority of the respondents involved in the study had low levels of correlating demographic profile and work environment practice which showed relatively no significance on their level of adherence to nursing care.

Recommendations

The result of this study shed light to areas of which the following points are recommended by the researchers:

Future studies are needed To develop a deeper understanding of its mechanism and effects, such studies will need to incorporate prospectively collected data on patient outcomes sensitive to nursing care quality. To define the threshold when rationing begins to affect patient outcomes negatively. To investigate the predictive evidence of the BERNCA instrument and the tool's value to measure and predict changes in the quality of care and patient outcomes. To enhance the reliability and validity of the BERNCA for use in other countries and areas, revisions of the instrument are recommended to reflect cultural and regional differences. A study to address this questions using data from the Rationing of Nursing Care and It's Relationship to Nurse Practice Environment in a Level 2 Private Hospital.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethics is an integral part of conducting research, especially when the proponents are dealing with the people, the community, pertinent documents, animals, and the like. An absolute observance was done and followed by the ethical consideration in conducting this study to avoid fallacy or misconceptions of the participant's views about the phenomenon under study, its integrity, and most especially to protect them from any harm by hiding their personal information using John Doe names. Lastly, the proponent asked the approval of the consent form from the participants, stating their rights and privileges including their role in the research.

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